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VIRTUAL WHITEBOARDS & DIGITAL POST-ITS – INCORPORATING INTERNET-BASED TOOLS FOR IDEATION INTO ENGINEERING COURSES

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ABSTRACT

Creativity plays an important role in the problem-solving process of engineering. Many engineering tasks can be understood as special cases of creative problem solving. Creative problem solving in companies often includes creative sessions in teams and the use of creativity techniques for groups such as brainstorming or morphological box, where ideas are recorded on a whiteboard with various visualization aids such as sticky notes. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, courses in creativity and innovation management in engineering curricula face the challenge of teaching creative problem solving, while the lecturer and the students work from home using cooperation platforms such as MS Teams or Zoom to interact. The functionality of these platforms with regard to ideation are limited so that internet-based tools for ideation can offer a sensible complement through e.g. virtual whiteboards enabling e-brainstorming sessions with spatially distributed participants. The paper gives an overview over internet-based tools for ideation (i.e. idea creation and idea evaluation) highlighting their functionality, templates and possible areas of use in engineering education with regard to creative problem solving. Furthermore, the paper discusses first experiences of teaching creative problem solving in a virtual environment including a feedback of students from a master course in industrial engineering.

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1 INTRODUCTION

The problem-solving process of engineering largely depends on the engineer's creativity. Several studies show that maintaining the performance of collaborative work such as creative problem solving in teams while working remotely is one of the biggest challenges during the COVID-19 pandemic [1, 2, 3]. First studies from industry [3] as well as research [4] indicate that workplace tools have a significant impact on productivity and creativity during remote work. According to Malhotra and Majchrzak [5] successful virtual workspaces need to supply two key features: "multichannel synchronous communication" and "support for maintaining a persistent record of knowledge over time". In the first category, the ideation process usually requires visualization tools such as whiteboards, presentation boards or flip charts where people can share their ideas using markers, cards and digital post-its. In a virtual workspace with remote members this has to be substituted with internet-based tools for ideation in the form of digital or virtual whiteboards and post-its. Lecturers of creativity and innovation management face similar challenges, as they instruct students in the tasks and techniques of creative problem solving, while both lecturer and students work from home using collaborative platforms such as MS Teams and Zoom. The functionality of these platforms with regard to ideation are limited so that digital whiteboards can offer a sensible complement. In this paper, the following chapter provides an overview of existing internet-based tools for ideation. Then, initial experiences in teaching creative problem solving with some of these tools are described. The last section concludes with a summary of the results and an outlook on future work.

2 INTERNET-BASED TOOLS FOR IDEATION

The creative process can be roughly divided into the phases of problem definition, ideation and solution implementation [6]. In the ideation part of the creative process there is typically an interplay of divergent and convergent tasks to generate and evaluate ideas. From these models we derived the following tasks which have to be supported by internet-based tools for ideation:

- Capturing ideas: Using templates and functions of creativity techniques
- Sorting ideas: Re-arranging ideas into relations, categories and hierarchies
- Developing ideas: Fleshing out existing ideas and specifying details
- Evaluating ideas: Assessing ideas to find the most promising one(s)

Additionally the tools need to enable the following two tasks to link the virtual to the real world:

- Documenting results: Generating a file for permanent storage
- Communicating: Using a direct audio/video communication channel for group interaction during ideation sessions

We chose ten common internet-based tools and assessed them based on the functions necessary to support these task (see table 1).

The results in table 1 show that on the one hand there are very simple tools such as Ideaboardz or Mindmeister with few functions, which can serve as an introduction into the field, and on the other hand there are comprehensive tools such as Miro, Conceptboard or Mural with lots of functionality, which can serve advanced needs but need more skills to master. However, it should be noted that table 1 is a snapshot in time. Tools can and do expand their range over time to include additional features. The data collection period for table 1 was from February to May 2021.

3 FIRST EXPERIENCES WITH DIGITAL WHITEBOARDS

First experiences with teaching creative problem solving in a virtual environment have been made in the context of a master course in industrial engineering at the University of Applied Sciences in Düsseldorf. The course called Innovation and Technology Management took place in the summer semester of 2020 (SS2020). During the course, the prospective engineers worked the entire semester of 14 sessions in groups of five on a self-chosen problem to redesign an everyday object ending with the students presenting their solutions. In total, there were 25 students divided into five groups. Students were trained in the basics of creative problem solving and creativity techniques in two lectures with exercises. In this context, it was asked which techniques the students were already familiar with. The assessment of the degree of familiarity shows a similar picture to that from the previous semester [7]. Students show a high familiarity with intuitive creativity techniques and three quarters of them have already participated in a brainstorming session. This is also reflected in the evaluation of various self-assessments from past semesters of the same course. Students prefer intuitive techniques such as brainstorming over others and would be most likely to use them to generate ideas [7,8].

Students from the SS2020 had to use e-brainstorming to generate ideas. The students used two tools selected by the lecturer, a simple tool (Ideaboardz) to capture ideas and a more complex tool (Miro) to facilitate further processes such as sorting and evaluating. After the ideation sessions, a survey was conducted to determine which form of brainstorming (traditional or online) is preferred by the students. Of the 25 students who participated in the course 19 evaluable questionnaires were submitted. The result of the assessment in fig. 1 shows that the majority of the students (63%) prefer traditional brainstorming to e-brainstorming (37%). However, in a more detailed evaluation, e-brainstorming gets higher ratings from students on most criteria. Most students think they were more creative personally (48%) and as a group (54%) when they used e-brainstorming (in comparison to 32% and 12% respectively). They also think an e-brainstorming session is more fun (55%), is easier to do (66%) and promotes a better understanding of creativity (40%) than traditional brainstorming (32%, 20% and 32% respectively). Only when asked which method students would prefer in the future traditional brainstorming (47%) receives a higher approval than e-brainstorming (39%). Students still seem to be unsure of internet-based tools for ideation: In

general they still prefer the traditional way of doing brainstorming, but they also perceive the advantages of the online tools. It could be that, in general, the students still assess brainstorming based on habit and need to gain more experience with the new tools for a meaningful assessment.

Fig. 1. Comparison between online and offline brainstorming (n = 19)

4 CONCLUSION

This paper gives an overview of ten common internet-based virtual whiteboards, which are meant to be used for idea generation, and gives an insight on first experiences in teaching creative problem solving with two of these tools. The overview has shown that there are tools that are very simple and have few functions and other tools that have advanced functions. However, it should be noted that the data was collected in the period from February to May 2021 and, thus, represents a snapshot in time. Tools can and do expand the functions offered over time. Initial experience in working with two of these tools (Ideaboardz and Miro) has shown that students in general prefer creative problem solving in the form of traditional brainstorming over online brainstorming via digital whiteboards. However, they also perceive the benefits of online tools, as in a more detailed evaluation, e-brainstorming receives higher ratings in comparison to traditional brainstorming. It should be considered that the evaluation is from a small sample size. A total of 25 students participated in the course, of which 19 submitted an evaluation. Future plans for the course include testing other digital whiteboards and repeating the survey with other students so that over time a larger sample size can be created and the results can be compared. As part of the review of the tools, in addition to the expansion of the table with additional tools, the continuous updating of the newly added features is also planned. Furthermore, an investigation can be carried out to determine in how far the individual tools are data protection compliant.

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